

inDICES

Measuring the Impact of Digital Culture

Deliverable 5.8

Cultural Heritage Institutions and the Digital Single Market MOOC

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870792.

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The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme (H2020-DT-GOVERNANCE-13-2019) under grant agreement n° 870792.

D5.8 – Cultural Heritage Institutions and the Digital Single Market MOOC

Version 1.0

28/10/2022

Grant Agreement number:	870792
Project acronym:	inDICES
Project title:	Measuring the impact of Digital CultureE
Funding Scheme:	H2020-DT-GOVERNANCE-13-2019
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Executive Summary

This document presents the development of a Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) on “Developing digital transition strategies for Cultural Heritage Institutions” to support cultural organizations in understanding the potential of Digital Transformation in the cultural sector and in developing a digital strategy. It describes the content and the stages necessary for the realization of the course, which was officially launched on September 26, 2022.

The MOOC, addressed primarily to professionals in the cultural industry and students of digital cultural heritage, was built around the four research topics that constitute the foundation of the *D3.2 Guidelines for CHIs Digital Transformation: Digital Trends & Participatory Culture, Empowering IPR for Cultural Heritage Institutions, Invigorating Collaborations & Organisational Growth, Approaching Innovation and Digital Strategies*.

The report starts by introducing the main concept behind the development of the MOOC as well as its primary objectives and it is followed by an overview of the features that set the foundation for the creation of the MOOC. In the second section “Why a MOOC”, elements such as the integration of interactive educational models, the collaboration between academia and cultural industry at the foundation of the course development, the target audience, and the future use of the MOOC are highlighted. The third paragraph on “Previous MOOC experience” discusses the already existing MOOCs on Digital Transformation and provides an overview of how the inDICEs MOOC inserts itself into KU Leuven's experience in developing humanities and projects-related MOOCs bringing it to a higher level. “Design and implementing the MOOC” is dedicated to the detailed description of the entire MOOC creation process, starting from the definition of the educational strategy to the design of learning activities and the creation of the content, until the launch of the MOOC and its dissemination. Finally, the last section is dedicated to an attempted analysis of the first, partial educational engagement data which results from the first run of the MOOC.

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1. Introduction: a MOOC on Digital Transition strategies in GLAM¹

The MOOC on Digital Transition Strategies for Cultural Heritage Institutions brings together the most interesting results of the research and analysis conducted in the past three years within the inDICEs project. It was developed using the edX environment - a non-profit platform established by Harvard and MIT in 2012 - and it is currently being hosted on the edX KU Leuven platform - KULEUVENX². The MOOC was officially launched on edX on the 26th of September 2022. It is currently running and will remain accessible until the 20th of November 2022, the end date of the first run of the course.

Developed thanks to a solid cooperation between inDICEs partners and specialists as well as experts from the KU Leuven MOOC development team, the course aims to raise awareness of the potential and impact of digital transformation strategies for cultural heritage institutions and to guide the learners in understanding how to best navigate the digital transformation realm and overcome its challenges. Differently from previous courses, this MOOC is in fact not uniquely taught for a purely academic audience but especially for professionals/aspiring professionals in the cultural heritage sector and the creative industry, policymakers, and cultural heritage students.

The course revolves around six modules. Each of them is dedicated to one of the project's Work Packages and represents a step toward a better understanding of the challenges as well as the possibilities that digital transition strategies can offer to cultural institutions. Participants are invited not only to build their comprehension around the concept of digital transformation and its potential for the cultural sector but also - thanks to the implementation of dedicated discussion forums within the learning environment - they are encouraged to share their experiences and actively discuss with the other participants.

Thus, from an educational point of view, the MOOC is envisioned not only as a traditional learning environment that allows participants to expand their knowledge on the topic but also as a place of professional growth. Through focused exercises, readings, video conversations, practical examples and the presentation of currently relevant case studies, the learners are encouraged not only to immediately put into practice their newly acquired knowledge but also to question their previous habits and assumptions and understand how to face new challenges.

¹ Part of this deliverable is based on the following conference paper with some adaptation in content and form: Pireddu, R., Truyen, F., Taes, S., Bocyte, R. (2022) inDICEs: a MOOC on Developing Digital Transition Strategies for Cultural Heritage Institutions, Proceedings of the 21st European Conference on e-Learning - ECEL 2022, Vol. 21, No. 1, pp. 425-43. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecel.21.1.904>

² <https://www.edx.org/school/kuleuvenx>

2. Why a MOOC?

Contrary to the original concept of MOOCs, which were meant as open online versions of university courses, and sometimes literally recordings of such classes, this MOOC fits in a series stemming directly from international research projects. Instead of delivering established academic knowledge to a wider audience, this MOOC is an example of an effort to shortcut the time of delivery of new knowledge to a professional audience. Besides the typical postgraduate students found in MOOCs, it is supposed to attract professionals and aspiring professionals, to make sure new insights reach the work floor.

A second aspect that sets this MOOC apart is the fact that the research does not only come from academic institutions, but emerges from a collaboration between university research departments and GLAM organisations. Both parties have good reasons to engage in these efforts. For the universities involved, research in collaboration with the professional field offers an important reality test and validation exercise for new ideas. It gives access to hitherto inaccessible resources, which are held, in our case, in heritage institutions. More importantly, it gives access to the audiences and stakeholders of these institutions. This facilitates new ventures such as e.g. Citizen Science projects.

Because of these elements, this MOOC does not entirely insert itself within the type of educational approach generally conceived by edX, which usually orients its courses towards a textbook-structure model (also recognized as xMOOC), favoring independent learning over interaction (Waller et al, 2019). Instead, it can be recognized as a dynamic learning environment that shares elements both with the xMOOC approach and the collaborative MOOC model (cMOOC) (Mary Queen & Vel Murugan, 2020). The integration of aspects belonging to both models aimed at creating an environment that could enhance knowledge acquisition through collaboration and connection among participants and not uniquely through passive learning (Wang et al. 2017, Siemens 2005). There are also more practical reasons universities want to connect their study programmes to the labour environment, such as, for example, facilitating job uptake not only for graduates but also for postdoctoral researchers, as there are many more PhD researchers than academic vacancies.

But how does a MOOC fit in all of this? A recent development in the business model of many universities, and in particular in Europe, is the elaboration of a micro-credential system.³ Currently, due to advanced digital platforms and tools offered by online learning solutions, there is a myriad of informal learning going on, which has difficulties connecting to formal learning. On the one hand, there is a need for a wide variety of very specific, job-oriented learning modules, on the other, there is a need for certification of knowledge and skills acquired in such a way. For universities, there is a clear motive to facilitate the transition from partial, specific learning components to degree learning. Micro-credentials are meant to play an important role in facilitating this.⁴ And, as it happens, a very flexible way to organise micro-credentials is to offer MOOCs.

³ See <https://education.ec.europa.eu/education-levels/higher-education/micro-credentials>

⁴ See e.g. <https://mce.eadtu.eu/> and for an attempt at definition <https://www.voced.edu.au/content/ngv:91634>

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It needs to be acknowledged that similar criticisms are being forwarded towards micro-credentials as were advanced against MOOCs during their introduction and hype in the period 2008-2012 (Daniel 2012; Boullier 2012; Holton 2012), such as that it doesn't solve structural problems in formal education (Boud & Jorre 2021), that it has too much of a focus on employability than on Bildung (Wheelahan & Moodie 2021), that its impact on the Higher Education business model is limited (McGreal & Olcott 2022). However, in this case, registered university students are also invited to join the MOOC as part of their formal classes, to attract better dialogue between students, aspiring professionals and professionals. Of course, part of the aim is improving employability, but it also encourages students to critically assess the current labour organisation in GLAM starting on a reflection of its declared core mission, which is part of the MOOC activity. It is a much more cyclic, integrative, two-way learning and teaching approach than the linear supply chain model which is presupposed by many critics. It actually brings institutional and expert knowledge into the academic program.

For the professional organisations, in our case from the heritage sector, contributing to the development of a MOOC and sharing their expertise would be beneficial in academia at an educational level. As participating in the MOOC is free, it is also a way to support in-house capacity building. This is the main reason why important GLAM network organisations were part of the innovation project behind the MOOC.

3. Previous MOOC experience

There are important differences between MOOC content and academic course content. One aspect is the difference in implicit context: while an academic course is embedded in a larger education program, and often builds further on previously taken courses, a MOOC is a stand-alone course. This also means that a lot of process information, which is normally given by the educational institution or the professor, needs to be made explicit in the MOOC.

There is also a difference in duration, as it does not really make sense to have one-hour recordings for the MOOC, as online consumption habits are quite different and oriented to shorter content digestion. This meant that for the development of this MOOC it needed to rely on in-house expertise at the university to develop the content as well as the learning activities in the MOOC. The support team at KU Leuven uses an ABC design model⁵ for this which allowed the design of a well-structured development environment. Luckily, for the current MOOC, the academic team also had previous experience with developing MOOCs for the humanities, such as “Europeana Space: Creative with Digital Heritage”, “Creating a Cultural Heritage Community” and Euro-noir: Cultural Identity in European Popular Crime Narratives⁶. This helped us to understand the mechanics of developing a coherent MOOC with the collaboration of distant, independent, multi-disciplinary research teams. Creating such a MOOC with a large number of contributing partners - in these cases including university research groups from engineering and a diversity of humanities disciplines, SME’s, large professional networks and non-profit/not-for-profit organisations - requires rigorous development and implementation planning. It also requires a lot of fine-tuning and the setup of a joint quality control and content “normalisation” procedures. For the MOOC student, the wording, style, formatting and presentation of the different content modules must be sufficiently aligned and of comparable accessibility level. This was a major undertaking requiring a quite elaborate editorial and reviewing protocol.

In the area of transformation and management in the cultural heritage sector, it is possible to find interesting examples of MOOCs - such as those gathered in the table below - which, however, fail to focus really on the importance of the digital turn for sustainable heritage work.

⁵https://www.kuleuven.be/onderwijs/werkvormen/activeren_studenten/ABCdesign/onderwijs-anders-bekeken

⁶ The MOOCs “Europeana Space: Creative with Digital Heritage” (EU CIP Funded), “Creating a Digital Cultural Heritage Community” (EU CEF Funded), and “Euro Noir: Cultural Identity in European Popular Crime Narratives” (Horizon 2020 Funded), all available on <https://www.edx.org/school/kuleuvenx>.

MOOC Title	Platform	Institution	Objectives/Focus
Digital Education with Cultural Heritage ⁷	European Schoolnet Academy	EF - Europeana Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide insights into educational potentials of digital cultural heritage • Guide the teachers to integrate digital cultural heritage in their classes
Cultural Heritage in Transformation ⁸	edX	RWTH Aachen University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management of tangible Cultural Heritage • Does not cover digital transformation in the institutional context
Arts and Culture: Towards a New Management Paradigm ⁹	edX	IIMBx - Indian Institute of Management, Bangalore	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economics approach • Not focused on the implications of the digital transition.
Arts and Heritage Management ¹⁰	Coursera	Bocconi University, Milan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focused on “art management”, and networking.
Tourism Management at UNESCO World Heritage Sites ¹¹	FUN MOOC	Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focused on communication technologies, economy, management and planning

⁷ <https://www.europeana.eu/en/europeana-classroom/moocs>

⁸ <https://www.edx.org/course/cultural-heritage-in-transformation>

⁹ <https://www.edx.org/course/arts-and-culture-towards-a-new-management-paradigm>

¹⁰ <https://www.coursera.org/learn/arts-heritage>

¹¹ <https://www.fun-mooc.fr/en/courses/?limit=21&offset=0&query=heritage>

4. Designing & implementing the MOOC

The course on Developing Digital Transformation Strategies for CHIs was thoroughly designed as an interactive, learning environment where professionals and students interested in the field could explore how to work on the challenges of digital transformation and put the newly acquired knowledge into practice.

Since the first stages of its development, the MOOC was designed on the basis of the set of recommendations included in the **D3.2 Guidelines for CHIs Digital Transformation**, which contained the major results of the main inDICEs research areas: digital transformation and self-assessment, digital trends, IPR, capacity building and value chains, impact assessment, and technological innovation. These research areas represented not only the different Work Packages of the project but also reflected the table of content of the MOOC.

As highlighted in the course structure below, the course is composed of a total of 6 modules, dedicated to meaningful topics in the digital transformation field. For each of them, an estimated effort of 3/4 hours per week is requested. The last module, which contains the final exam of the course in the form of multiple-choice quizzes, is also available for those students who want to upgrade their status and enroll in the **verified-track**. Upon successful completion of the final exam they receive an official certificate.

1. Digital Transformation and Self-Assessment
Introduction
1 Introduction on Digital Transformation for CHIs
2 Self-Assessment for CHIs: strategies and challenges
Conclusion

2. Digital Trends and Culture 3.0
Introduction
1 From culture 1.0 to 3.0: regimes of cultural production
2 The role of digital platforms and social media
3 The impacts of digital cultural participation
4 Trendwatching
Conclusion

3. Empowering IPR for the commons
Introduction
1 Empowering IPR for the commons
2 IPR: the essentials
3 Policy vision & implementation
Conclusion

4. Strategic skills, collaborations & organization growth
Introduction
1 Value creation chains
2 Capacity Building
3 Networks
Conclusion

5. Impact Assessment
Introduction
1 Impact Assessment
Conclusion

6. Approaching Technological Innovation
Introduction
1 Creating public spaces online
2 Comprehensive digital strategies & innovation
3 Creating an online engagement strategy
Conclusion

The creation process of the MOOC included several important stages, which usually helped the team committed to the development of the MOOC in realizing a thorough and robust educational framework. These steps consisted of:

1. Writing the edX About Page
2. Sketching the Course Design Plan
3. Designing the educational activities
4. Creating the content
5. Uploading and editing/reviewing the content on the edX platform
6. Promoting the MOOC

4.1 Writing the edX About Page

The About Page can be considered the first step to be taken in a MOOC implementation process since it represents the first opportunity for the MOOC creators to sketch the structure of the future MOOC. This document, also referred to as the MOOC promotional page, is showcased on the edX platform and contains all the information about the MOOC that can be relevant for the students. Generally, it includes a description of the course, its goals, the length, the prerequisite, and the learning approach, as well as information on the instructors. The About Page is an essential element in the dissemination and promotion of the MOOC since it provides the most relevant details for the students to understand whether they could be interested in following the course. Within the creation of the inDICEs MOOC, the creation of the About Page was monitored through the feedback given by the KU Leuven MOOC Team and finalized through the collaboration between KU Leuven and the other partner institutions collaborating with the MOOC.

The image shows a screenshot of a MOOC course page on the KU LeuvenX platform. At the top left, the KU Leuven logo is visible. The main title of the course is "Developing Digital Transition Strategies for Cultural Heritage Institutions". Below the title, there is a subtitle: "How to develop and implement effective digital strategies in Cultural Heritage Institutions". To the right of the title is a colorful abstract graphic with a "Play Video" button. Below the title and subtitle, there are three icons representing course details: a clock icon for "8 weeks" (3-4 hours per week), a person icon for "Instructor-paced" (Instructor-led on a course schedule), and a dollar sign icon for "Free" (Optional upgrade available). Below these details, there is a section titled "There is one session available:" with a note that after the session ends, it will be archived. At the bottom, there is a box containing the start and end dates: "Starts Sep 26" and "Ends Nov 20", along with a red button that says "Enrolled: Go to course".

Fig. 1. Detail of the published MOOC About Page on KULeuvenX

4.2 Sketching the Course Design Plan

Together with the About Page, the course design plan represented an important step for the definition of the concept and the goals of the MOOC since it constituted the first stage in the

creation of the MOOC structure. In the Course Design Plan are sketched both a first educational framework of the future course and ideas on the topics that should be tackled. It also contains the “learning goals”, a set of statements that indicate which kind of knowledge the learners should ideally master by following each module.

KULeuvenX Course Design Plan

Section/ Module #	Module name (topic/concept)	Desired results (Learning outcomes per module)	Course ideas/ (existing) course material (activities/resources)
<i>Module 0</i>	Getting started: The learner gets familiar with the platform as well as with the learning goals of the course. They virtually meet the instructors and they understand how the course is structured from an educational point of view.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome and overview • Understand the course's purposes. • Gain insight into the workload and main topics of this course • Understand how the online course works • Getting familiar with edX MOOCs • Learn how to study for this course 	<p>Read about the purpose of this course</p> <p>Meet your instructors</p> <p>Read syllabus & the learning goals</p> <p>Get familiar with the context in which this course was developed</p> <p>Discover more about the learning methods used in this course & introduce the idea behind the use of the self-assessment tool</p> <p>Participate in discussion: Introduce yourself, motivate your participation & your expectations</p>
Module 1	Introduction: Digital Transitions, monitoring & self-assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the main concept behind the notion of digital transformation (DT) • Discover through selected case studies how DT can be used to support CHIs • Identify and compare the most recent development related to assessment and monitoring strategies 	<p>Complete</p> <p>Watch</p> <p>Read</p> <p>Add</p>
	<p>Main modules subsections:</p> <p>1. Digital Transformation in CHIs</p> <p>2. Assessment & Monitoring strategies: an overview</p> <p>3. Self-Assessment-Tool</p>	In this module, the students receive an introduction to the main concepts that will be tackled in the course. They also start learning about the self-assessment tool.	

Fig. 2. Detail from the Course Design Plan document

4.3 Designing the educational activities

The design of the main, basic structure of the MOOC was followed by a thorough definition of the educational structure of the course. This included the structure of the module's subsections and the description of the learning activities, essential for reaching the MOOC's learning goal.

These elements were conceived during the collaborative ABC Design Session, a training session led by the KU Leuven MOOC development team.

The ABC Learning Design concept is based on the theory that Prof. Diana Laurillard (UCL) developed in her book “Teaching as a design science” (2012), where fundamentals of learning theories are combined together with instructional design principles in order to set up the basis of the student's knowledge creation. These learning theories were then applied to the MOOC design session during a 90 minutes workshop where participants are supervised in sketching the learning activities through

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the use of a visual storyboard. This allows participants to thoroughly structure each module of the online course on the basis of the type of content they want to offer and the learning outcomes.

This provided all the partners involved in the MOOC production with the right tools for understanding the MOOCs’ structure and for creating educational activities, which consist of a set of assignments (in the form of videos, reading material, quizzes, discussion, etc.) necessary for the students to understand a certain topic and to assess their comprehension of the content.

The first ABC Session was followed by the creation of a structured program of monthly meetings with the partner institutions involved in the production of the MOOC. In these sessions, the teams were guided through the development of their own module. Even in a distant environment, the collaboration was made possible using Skype calls and a collaborative Google Drive folder. The latter allowed a simultaneous collaboration between the inDICES partners and the MOOC development team of KU Leuven despite the geographical distance.

In the extract from the design of module 1 shown below, it is possible to see the excerpt from the first tables used to realize the structure of the modules.

Module 1: Introduction: Digital Transformation & self-assessment

Module 1: Introduction: Digital Transformation & self-assessment							
Subsection: Introduction on digital transformation for CHIs							
Learning activity 1 (Learning activity 2)	Inquiry	Acquisition	Acquisition	Acquisition	Practice	Acquisition	Inquiry Discussion
What	Word cloud	Text	Glossary of DT terms	Literature Review	Quiz on DT	Video Interview	Discussion exercise
Materials	Question	Text		List of OA articles	Multiple choice	Video/Podcast	Practical exercise
Content	Images cloud - which image do they associate with the term "Digital Transformation"?	Introduction to DT (Europeana Pro + include NEMO survey) results - literature review)				Interviews with different organizations: what did transformation mean to them? Series of 5 minute videos/podcast	Split into two groups: are you a heritage professional? Yes > Present your own institution/ecosystem to me of the
Who		Fred	Roberta	Fred	Roberta	Rasa	Rasa
Status							
Subsection: Self-Assessment for CHIs: strategies and challenges							
Learning activity 1 (Learning activity 2)	Acquisition	Acquisition	Practice Inquiry	Acquisition			
What	Text	Text with slideshow	Exercise	Introductory text			
Materials	Informative Text	Informative Text/Slideshow	Exercise	Text			
Content	Overview of cases - already existing self-assessment tools (Collections Trust, DEN, Microsoft, ...)	Explore relevant case studies (Enumerate, Microsoft, Spectrum, examples from their	Use evaluation grid to assess the case studies you found	Short intro into the participatory platform and the upcoming modules			

Fig. 3. ABC Design Document - Creation of Module 1

At a later stage, after the establishment of the educational activities and MOOC structure, it was decided to complement the so-called ABC Design Document with another collaborative table, called Activity Planning & Content Inventory document, which had the main function to monitor the educational activities production status.

InDICES MOOC Activities Planning **XLSX** ☆ 📄 🌐

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Module	Type	Section	Number	Title	Length (minutes)	Who	Projected Delivery Date	Status
Module 1 - Intro: Digital Transformation & Self-Assessment								
1	video	Introduction	M1 V1	Intro to module 1		Sofie		Neils is editing
1	text	Introduction	M1 T1	Learning goals		Roberta		To do team CS
1	exercise	Introduction on digital transformation for CHIs	M1 E1	Images cloud	10'	Rasa		Draft delivered
1	video	Introduction on digital transformation for CHIs	M1 V2	Introduction to DT		Fred		This is the one current
1	text	Introduction on digital transformation for CHIs	M1 T3	Glossary of DT terms		Roberta		To do team CS
1	text	Introduction on digital transformation for CHIs	M1 T4	Defining digital transformation		Sofie		To do team CS
1	quiz	Introduction on digital transformation for CHIs	M1 Q1	Quiz on DT		Roberta		To do team CS
1	video	Introduction on digital transformation for CHIs	M1 V2	Interviews with organizations		Fred/Rasa		Rasa
1	exercise	Introduction on digital transformation for CHIs	M1 E2	Case study presentation		Fred/Rasa		Draft delivered
1	exercise	Introduction on digital transformation for CHIs	M1 E3	Match the scenarios		Fred/Rasa		Draft delivered
1	text	Self-Assessment for CHIs: strategies and challenges	M1 T5	SATs overview	10'	Roxanne		Delivered
1	exercise	Self-Assessment for CHIs: strategies and challenges	M1 E4	Explore case studies		Rasa		Draft delivered
1	exercise	Self-Assessment for CHIs: strategies and challenges	M1 E5	Discussion on scenarios		Fred/Rasa		Draft delivered
1	text	Self-Assessment for CHIs: strategies and challenges	M1 T7	State of the art in assessment		Sofie		To do team CS

3. Empowering IPR 4. Strategic Skills... 5. Impact Assessment 6. Approaching technological in Content Inventory

Fig. 4. Detail from “Content Inventory” document

4.4 Creating the content

Once the educational framework of the MOOC appeared clear and well structured, the work proceeded with the creation of the educational material to be included in the online course. This stage consisted of developing and gathering three primary types of content:

- Text
- Multimedia content
- Assessment

Text. This category includes academic publications, informative texts, blog posts, glossaries, or suggested readings. They needed to be not only fully accessible (in the case of academic articles) but also, especially for producing informative, clear, concise, and readable texts.

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Reading | Digital Transformation Glossary

 Bookmark this page

In the section below, you will find a **glossary** with important and useful terms in the field of **Digital Transformation**. This small lexicon might be useful for you while you navigate through this MOOC. Are you familiar with all of them? Or are some of the concepts still new to you?

STAFF DEBUG INFO

Glossary

Digital Transformation ↑

Digital transformation is both the process and the result of using digital technology to transform how an organisation operates and delivers value. It helps an organisation to thrive, fulfil its mission and meet the needs of its stakeholders. In the cultural heritage context, it enables CHIs to contribute to the transformation of a sector powered by digital and a Europe powered by culture. (Europeana)

Digitization ↑

It refers to the making of analog information digital (for example text, sound, or image) in order to ease its storage, sharing, process, and transfer.

Digitalization ↑

It refers not only to the transformation of analog information into a digital format, which allows making them available to a broader public, but it includes the effects of digitization on different levels such as the availability, accessibility, usability, and reusability, participation.

Digital strategy ↓

Crowdsourcing ↓

CHIs ↓

Digital Maturity ↓

Fig. 5. Example of a glossary

Multimedia content. Another essential element of MOOCs is represented by the multimedia material. The online course on Digital Transformation for CHIs was in fact enriched not only with talking head videos and screencasts but also with video interviews with experts coming from GLAMs and Cultural industries authors. Pivotal in this context, was the support given by Sound and Vision for the recording of a good part of the multimedia material and for the support during the video post-processing. This content was produced following strict visual and technical guidelines as well as respecting the visual identity of the project. The use of different multimedia techniques for presenting the content was chosen in order to ensure interactivity and diversity in the learning process. This category also includes the production of the MOOC **trailer**, which was produced by KU Leuven and supported by LIMEL's video artists and video producers. The trailer was conceived as a way to present the main topics tackled in the MOOC as well as the main goals of the online course, respecting the graphic identity of the project, also used throughout the whole course.

Video | Theory vs. practice: a conversation

Bookmark this page

In the section below, you will find an interview with **Lizzy Jongma** (Senior ICT Project Leader, Dutch Network for War Collections WW2 (NOB)) on value chains and their application to the heritage sector.

Lizzy Jongma is senior ICT expert with vast experience in managing cultural heritage data in the digital environment, supporting cultural heritage institutions to embrace and make the most of the new technologies. She worked as data manager at the Rijksmuseum and currently works for The Network of Dutch War Resources - a national network of heritage institutions with WWII related collections. The goal of the network is to develop digital services, products and strategies to make these resources digitally available, traceable and (re-)usable. She is also a Board member of Wikimedia NL.

STAFF DEBUG INFO

Video

We started at
Rijksstudio at the Rijksmuseum with a very practical problem. The museum was closed for six years already due to renovations and so the vast collections of the Rijksmuseum were inaccessible to most people and there was a small sub-museum where you could go and see some of the highlights, but the vast majority of 2 million objects were stored away and inaccessible for the public. So

Fig. 6. A video interview displayed in the MOOC

Exercises. It includes a variety of assessment elements which goes from multiple choice quizzes to case studies presentations, from prompting discussion through specific questions to producing original material. The goal is to allow learners to put into practice what they have learned in the modules but also by sharing their own experiences to question their previous habits and understand how to face new challenges. Another element in this context is represented by the integration of exercises where the learners were encouraged to explore new digital tools, such as the Europeana Impact Playbook, or those directly developed in the context of the inDICES project, such as the Self-Assessment tool or the Visual Analytics Dashboard.

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Discussion assignment | Case study presentation

🔖 Bookmark this page

Discussion assignments due Nov 20, 2022 12:00 CET
 Select a concrete example where digital heritage collections were used to create a new experience, product or service. This could be an online exhibition, a digital museum shop, etc.

If you cannot think of your own example, choose one of the following:

- GIF IT UP competition <https://gfitup.net/>
- BBC RemArc project <https://remarc.bbcrewind.co.uk/>
- Historiana portal for educators <https://historiana.eu/>

Based on this example, answer the following questions:

1. Briefly describe your selected example (1-2 sentences). If possible, include reference links.
2. What technological processes were necessary to execute it?
3. What type of skills were needed to execute it? What type of organisations might have been involved in its execution?
4. Who are the target audiences of your example and how are they being reached?
5. Share your answer in the **discussion forum** below.

STAFF DEBUG INFO

Self-evaluation discussion assignment

1 point possible (graded)

Did you post a substantive answer to the question and/or write a substantive comment in response to someone else's post?

Yes

No

Fig. 7. Discussion assignment

4.5 Educational strategy

The MOOC on Developing Digital Transformation Strategies for CHIs aims to tap into the many potentialities of distance learning and, at the same time, foster engagement and participation among the students. In order to reach this result, the MOOC was developed using the following approaches:

The adoption of an instructor-paced learning environment, where learners need to follow a certain learning schedule in order to complete the MOOC. The material included in each module is released on a weekly basis. This method not only encourages students to follow the course methodically but also facilitates dialogue and discussion among the participants, reducing the risk of lack of participation.

Possibility to create a personalized trajectory. Although the students are encouraged to follow the course respecting the order of the module, each module is also designed to exist independently from one another. This enables MOOCs participants to create their own learning trajectory and to freely choose the modules to follow depending on their own needs and interests.

Use of external tools to expand users' learning experience. Participants' learning experience is extended outside the learning platform through the inclusion of external tools such as the inDICEs Self-Assessment-Tool, the Visual Analytics Dashboard (VAD), or the Europeana Impact Playbook. The combination of different environments aims not only at supporting a diversity of activities but also at upgrading the learning experience with further interactive elements.

Blended-learning. Besides being worldwide available on the edX platform for all the students interested in the topic, the course is also designed to be included within a blended learning environment in the context of dedicated digital cultural heritage courses offered at KU Leuven.

Conversations with the experts. Each module of the MOOC includes video interviews with professionals coming from different European cultural institutions. From an educational point of view, it is essential that students can also learn directly from the experience of professionals in the sector.

4.6 Content uploading on the edX platform

The material creation and gathering were followed by the proofreading and editing process. The content was in fact proofread by a professional team and formatted so that it would visually match the platform layout.

At the end of this process, the content was finally uploaded on edX. This was done by the CS Digital team who organized and added the material to the platform using a specific edX tool called Studio. This tool made it possible not only to organize the content online but also to manage the whole course, allowing, during the running of the course, constant interaction also with the learners.

4.7 MOOC promotion

At the very beginning of September 2022, three weeks before the official release of the MOOC, the official promotion plan of the MOOC started. This included:

- MOOC dissemination and promotion on all the inDICEs social media networks (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn).
- Promotion by all the partner institutions participating in the inDICEs project.
- Promotion of the trailer and MOOC concept by the edX consortium through edX networks and platforms.
- Presentation of the MOOC on Developing Digital Transformation Strategies for CHIs at the Europeana Conference 2022.

5. Insights into learner engagement and demographic

MOOCs can be important tools for disseminating academic and institutional research results and easing free access to educational content. Also, they can be an excellent instrument for educators to understand learners' backgrounds and evaluate their involvement, engagement, participation and interaction with the proposed educational material. Also, these educational data might be crucial for understanding how the learning environment can be best improved (Onah 2018).

This can usually be done through the analysis of the MOOC's learning analytics. Open edX allows the instructors to access these data through graphs and visualizations directly on the platform. Many data are, in fact, generated by the learner's interaction with the platform in the form of logs, events, activities such as comments in the discussion forums, and feedback (Chahuan and Goel 2017). This data can provide information not only on the learning progress and class grades but also on the learner's provenance, age, etc. The evaluation and analysis of this data can help instructors both interpret the information and consequently improve the learning environment and also gain insight into the learner's behavior and preferences. Since a large part of the learning process is taking place online, statistics can help to monitor not only learner retention, participation, and performance, but also to verify the take-up and suitability of the course contents.

5.1 EdX *Insights* tool

The analysis of the learning analytics can be explored using the edX tool *Insights*, where educational data can be downloaded in .xlsx format. The data can be then visualized either directly on the platform or using data visualization tools.

The data showcased in this report are partial and are the result of the first 5 weeks of the first run of the MOOC on Developing Digital Transition Strategies for CHIs, launched on Monday, 26 September 2022. The MOOC will end on Sunday, 20 November 2022.

They are reported and evaluated here in order to trace a first, hypothetical pattern and general tendency in learners' demographic. The data analyzed include the number of participants, their gender, their background and their geographical provenance.

Fig. 8. Graph representing the daily enrollment rate of the MOOC

a. Number of students

The data below represent the number of overall students enrolled in the first run of the MOOC until 28 October 2022.

b. Gender

The following graph reveals the average gender of the MOOCs participants. From this chart, a very high percentage (70.9%) of female participants clearly emerges. The percentage of male students is 24.1%. This suggests that especially female learners are more interested in the topics explored in the MOOC.

c. Educational background

The third type of data examined is related to the educational background of the participants. From the graph below it appears quite clear that the highest percentage of students, who declared their education, possess a Master's degree. This data would suggest that the MOOC attracted participants with an advanced educational background and possibly with a knowledge of the dynamics explored in the online course.

d. Geographical distribution

Finally, the following chart and table below reveal the geographical provenance of the MOOC participants. From the data, it is evident that the highest percentage of participants comes from Spain (12.8%), Belgium (11.7%) and The Netherlands (8.0%). However, the MOOC managed to reach out to participants all over the world.

Geographic Breakdown [Download CSV](#)

Country or Region	Percent	Current Enrollment
Spain	12.8%	35
Belgium	11.7%	32
Netherlands	8.0%	22
Italy	7.7%	21
Greece	6.9%	19
United Kingdom	4.4%	12
Germany	3.3%	9
Portugal	3.3%	9
United States of America	3.3%	9
Turkey	2.9%	8

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6. Conclusion

The aim of this report was to give a detailed overview, on the one hand, of the main concepts and objectives at the basis of the development of the MOOC on Developing Digital Transition Strategies for Cultural Heritage Institutions as well as the many different stages that led to the creation of the educational environment. On the other hand, it intended to provide some partial results of the analysis carried out with the data coming from educational data available on the edX platform.

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